

White Paper

Patient Involvement in the Governance of the German Human Genome-Phenome Archive (GHGA)

Patients' perspectives and recommendations for implementation

Authors:

Eric Apondo, Andreas Bruns, Andrea Züger, Katja Mehlis, Anne Müller, Frank Brunsmann, Jan Eufinger, Simon Parker, Christoph Schickhardt, Eva Winkler and the GHGA Consortium

NATIONALES CENTRUM
FÜR TUMORERKRANKUNGEN
HEIDELBERG

getragen von:
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KLINIKUM
HEIDELBERG

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Executive Summary

The German Human Genome-Phenome Archive (GHGA) is committed to addressing the needs and expectations of patients through patient participation and the development of appropriate governance structures (1). To explore patient perspectives on patient involvement in the governance of genomic data archives (GDAs) in general and possible forms of patient involvement in the governance of GHGA specifically, the GHGA Ethics Working Group (EA, AB, AZ, CS, EW) designed a participatory study in which we conducted two deliberative forums in July 2022 with 26 participants from the cancer and rare diseases communities¹ in Germany. Two patient co-researchers (AM and FB), one each from the cancer and the rare diseases communities, were involved in designing and planning the study. In addition, we organised a follow-up consensus-building dialogue event in March 2023, bringing together study participants and representatives from GHGA to discuss unresolved issues from the forums and seek consensus on a concept for implementing patient involvement in the governance of GHGA. The dialogue event was attended by 17 of the initial 26 forum participants as well as 9 GHGA members.

The following were the main points raised by the forum participants. The participants:

- expressed a general willingness to support (secondary) medical research by sharing their genomic data,
- stressed the importance of data protection and privacy, but argued that it is also important to increase the usability of data for research,
- identified outreach activities as one of the main functions that would benefit from patient involvement,
- expressed an interest in being involved in data access procedures, insofar as this can be made possible,
- broadly supported a governance model with patient involvement through patient representatives².

¹ The forums were conducted with patients with active or cured cancer or rare diseases, individuals with predispositions to cancer or rare diseases, as well as their close family members. Some participants had experience as patient representatives. This broader definition of 'patient' is in keeping with recent literature on patient involvement in health care systems and research, where it is now used to refer to "any individual or group with lived experience of a health or health systems issue, including family members [and] caregivers" (see Manafa et al, 2018).

² In this white paper, 'patient representatives' refers to patients who are meaningfully involved in and bring the patient perspective to decision-making processes in an organisation.

The main elements of the concept developed in collaboration with the participants for implementing patient involvement in the governance of GHGA are as follows:

Establishment of a Patient Advisory Board (PAB) in GHGA

Patient involvement through patient representatives who constitute a Patient Advisory Board (PAB). The PAB should initially have 4 members.

Recruitment

The patient representatives should be recruited through an application process in collaboration with patient organisations.

Acknowledgement and compensation

The contributions of patient representatives should be acknowledged in the products of GHGA projects. The patient representatives should be financially compensated for their work.

Continuous training

GHGA should make resources available for continuous training of patient representatives.

Involvement of data controllers

Data Controllers³ are responsible for data access and organising data access procedures. They should be involved in operationalising and increasing the impact of meaningful patient involvement.

The following pages present the findings of the deliberative forums, as well as results of the consensus-building dialogue event, in more detail.

³ Article 4 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (2) defines a Data Controller as the “natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data” (Art. 4, Paragraph 7). In this paper, the Data Controllers are the hospitals, sequencing centers and biobanks which will submit data to GHGA (see Eufinger et al., 2021).

1. Introduction and Background

The World Health Organization (WHO) supports involving patients in all levels of health care to enhance accountability and facilitate mutual understanding between patients and other actors in the health system (3). The German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) also advocates for patient involvement, arguing that it improves research outcomes by shifting research focus to areas of patient need, thereby ultimately improving patient care. Moreover, the BMBF has identified health care and research involving genetic data as areas which benefit from patient involvement (4).

Like genomic databases, GDAs are “electronic collections of genomic data that have been derived from human biological samples, which are made available to researchers under certain conditions” (5). However, GDAs are usually collections from already existing data systems (6) designed for integrating and sharing data (7, 8). In this paper, patient involvement in GDAs is defined as “meaningful and active collaboration” with patients or their representatives in activities and practices of a GDA, including governance (9). Governance of an organisation refers to “processes of decision-making [and regulation], whether through laws, norms, power or language” (10). Effective patient involvement in GDA governance frameworks can contribute to compliance with legal requirements and to ethically sound data use (9).

GHGA is committed to addressing the needs and expectations of patients, and to enhancing transparency and accountability through meaningful patient involvement (1). This collaborative approach, if well implemented, can help build trust and create strong long-term relationships with patient groups (11). Recent literature has shown that, in Germany, the level of patient involvement in healthcare, including in the management of personal health data, is low and needs improvement (12), and that patients are generally “grossly underrepresented” (13) in healthcare governance. Ensuring transparency in the governance of GDAs by means of patient involvement is widely seen as best practice (14) and is key in securing society’s approval and trust to use patient data for research (15). There are, however, no set standards for involving patients in the governance of GDAs as it is a highly context-specific process which must consider the cultural, social, and legal context of the GDA, as well as its aims and resources (9). Therefore, in order to effectively implement patient involvement in the governance of GHGA, there was a need to first explore the expectations and concerns of German patients for trustworthy governance of GDAs, on which we report in this document. This white paper also proposes a concept for implementing patient involvement in the governance of GHGA within its current framework of goals, policies and procedures.

2. Methods and Processes

2.1. The deliberative forums and the dialogue event

This white paper is based on findings from two deliberative forums conducted in July 2022 with participants recruited from the German cancer and rare diseases communities, as well as a consensus-building follow-up event which took place in March 2023. The forums were planned and designed with two patient co-researchers, one each from the cancer and the rare diseases communities. The co-researchers co-authored the study protocol. They were also involved in important aspects of the study design, including developing the discussion guide for the deliberative forums as well as the education materials that participants received prior to the forums. Further, they were involved in developing the recruitment strategy and sent out invitations to potential participants nationwide through the mailing lists of the following organisations:

- i. Allianz Chronischer Seltener Erkrankungen (ACHSE): ACHSE is the German umbrella organisation for persons with chronic rare diseases and their relatives. It has over 130 member organisations, the smallest having 30, the largest over 7.500 members (16).
- ii. Haus der Krebs-Selbsthilfe (HKSH): HKSH consists of 10 nationwide member associations, including the national self-help groups for prostate, colon, breast and ovarian cancers (17).
- iii. Bundesarbeitsgemeinschaft Selbsthilfe (BAG Selbsthilfe), with currently 123 nationwide organisations for chronically ill and disabled persons(18).

We conducted two separate, one-day long, live online forums on the 9th (10 participants) and 23rd (16 participants) of July 2022. Prior to the forums, the participants received information on GDAs generally, such as information on the ethical challenges associated with governance of GDAs, and GHGA in particular. During the forums, the participants discussed their motivations for giving their genomic data to GDAs. They also explored possible roles and forms of patient involvement in the governance of GDAs. The deliberative forums were evaluated after completion: the forum participants filled out a questionnaire after the forums to give feedback about the quality of the discussions. They also filled out pre- and post-questionnaires which measured knowledge gain and opinion-shift through the deliberative forums. The results of the evaluation will be the subject of a separate publication.

The findings of the deliberative forums were summarised in a draft document (in German) that was sent to the forum participants for feedback in February 2023. We invited all the forum participants to a follow-up two-hour, online dialogue event which took place on 4th March, 2023. 17 participants attended the event. 9 members of the GHGA-Team, representing the directorate, project coordination, data management, outreach, legal and ethics teams, were also present. In the dialogue event, unresolved matters from the forums as well as practical aspects of the implementation of the suggestions of the forum participants were discussed.

2.2 How this white paper was developed

After conducting the deliberative forums, this white paper was developed as follows (Figure 1):

The deliberative forums were transcribed verbatim. We conducted a qualitative analysis of the transcripts and summarised the findings in a draft document. The GHGA Ethics Working Group then sought input from GHGA members, which was included in a draft document; in preparation for the dialogue event, a German translation of the document was sent out to the forum participants in February 2023.

During the follow-up-dialogue event in March 2023, feedback was given on the draft document. The participants did not express any objections to the representation of their feedback from the forums. They did, however, expand on certain themes from the forums. Additionally, consensus was sought on topics from the deliberative forums on which there was a divergence of opinions.

Finally, the decisions from the dialogue event were included in the draft document, making it a summary of participant feedback and input from GHGA members from and after both events. GHGA members were again given the opportunity to give their input, after which the white paper was finalised.

Figure 1: Steps in the study and development of this white paper

3. Results

3.1 Patient perspectives on storage, sharing and secondary use of data in GDAs

3.1.1 Motivations and hopes for sharing data for secondary research

The forum participants were strongly in favour of having their data stored in a GDA and used for secondary research. Indeed, most of the participants or their family members had already been requested to give their data or had consented to secondary research use of their data. By giving their data, they hoped to increase the amount of data available for research and facilitate the integration of different international sources of genomic data. The participants saw research as essential to improving health care for current and future generations.

The participants were strongly in favour of having their data stored in a GDA and supporting genomic research, if certain conditions are fulfilled.

The participants acknowledged the impact that genomic research has had on the treatment of various illnesses. They hoped that making more data available would foster genomic research and expedite the integration of genomic aspects into the standards of clinical practice. Closely associated with this was the hope that by providing their data, they would more quickly learn about results of studies in which their data are used and about new developments or treatment approaches regarding their particular illness.

3.1.2 Data protection

The participants' opinions on data protection varied widely. Concerns with data protection were raised for all stages of the data management cycle, including acquisition, processing and storage, and release to researchers. Participants who are part of a patient organisation reported that there is mistrust and uncertainty among some patient groups about how safe their data are, who is using them, and who benefits from them.

Participants stressed the importance of data protection, but also emphasised that the usability and value of data for research should be increased.

Although some participants mentioned data protection and privacy as concerns, for many participants, increasing data potential for research was also very important. In this regard, the participants observed the need for transparency, which, in their view, could be achieved by involving patients or patient representatives in decision-making bodies and making information available to them about how data are used, when and for what purposes the data are transferred, and who makes decisions about data use and access. The participants felt it is important that a GDA can demonstrate that

knowledge gain and improvement of patient care have priority over other, especially financial, interests of the institutions handling their data.

3.1.3 Consent

The participants showed an in-depth understanding of consent processes from their personal experience and from the information that was provided before and during the forums. Most expressed a high willingness to donate data for secondary research under broad consent⁴. Participants who supported broad consent over other consent models believed it to be necessary to facilitate research. Moreover, most participants predicted that dynamic consent⁵ would likely be a burden on research participants. However, the participants acknowledged the advantages of dynamic over static consent models, mainly as pertains to the control that they would maintain over their data, especially considering new research methods and future directions of research. In this regard, they felt that patient involvement in governance, if well implemented, could play an important role in enhancing transparency and responsible use of data.

Most participants supported the use of broad consent as a model for GDAs, but noted that it has limits. They also noted that clear strategies for managing and communicating incidental findings are lacking.

Some participants reported having previously declined to share their data for secondary research, due to lack of clear strategies for communicating and managing incidental findings. They stated that, for patients, the possibility of incidental findings can be unsettling and worrying. They emphasised that they needed to feel, as part of the information process leading to consent, that incidental findings would be handled responsibly. Another reason that was mentioned for withholding consent was the lack of clear information on the aims and limits of research.

3.1.4 Cooperation with pharmaceutical companies

Some participants were sceptical about having their data shared with pharmaceutical companies. However, other participants noted that although involvement of commercial actors in research is often negatively connotated, it is necessary for development of innovative medica-

The participants stated that cooperation and data sharing with pharmaceutical companies should be accompanied by clear and transparent communication and consent guidelines.

⁴ Broad consent is "a single informed consent for future research uses of [...] data, but with external and ongoing oversight and governance by an institutional review board (IRB), research ethics committee (REC) or comparable entity"(19) of research projects.

⁵ Dynamic consent describes "personalised, online consent and communication platforms" (20) that allow data subjects to "access and modify their consent preferences continuously" (21).

tions and diagnostic procedures. They felt that the focus should not be on what kind of organisation a GDA is cooperating with, but on what is being done with the data. These participants explicitly supported closer cooperation and data-sharing with pharmaceutical companies, provided that clear, transparent guidelines are followed. For example, the participants expressed the view that the potential sharing of data with such companies should be explicitly mentioned in consent documents. Many participants speaking from personal experience with consent procedures noted however, that such information was often lacking in consent documents. It was also noted that patients should, if possible, be given the option to accept or reject data sharing with pharmaceutical companies specifically.

The participants also discussed how GDAs could encourage pharmaceutical companies to foster patient involvement in research, especially in cases where these companies profit scientifically and financially from data that have been generated through public funding. It was suggested that patient involvement in research projects of pharmaceutical companies should be a criterion for granting them access to data generated through publicly funded research. According to the participants, this would benefit individual patients involved in research and empower patient groups.

3.1.5 Keeping patients informed about research

The forum participants expressed a keen interest in receiving information about planned, ongoing, and completed research projects. They expressed the wish to be informed regularly about results of research being done with data stored in a GDA, possibly after choosing which research areas are of interest to them or relevant to their illness. Avenues that were mentioned included continuous online updates and electronic or print newsletters. It was suggested that receiving such information might increase patients' willingness to share data with GDAs, build and maintain trust, and demonstrate the impact of patient data for research.

The participants stated that patients should be updated about studies and study results.

3.2 Patients' recommendations for implementing patient involvement in the governance of GDAs

3.2.1 GDA governance tasks in which patients should be involved

The forum participants felt that patients should be involved as broadly and at as many points of the GDA governance structures as possible. On the other hand, to avoid tokenism, they stressed that patients should only participate in areas of governance where they can exercise

The forum participants identified communication and outreach activities, as well as data access procedures, as priority areas for patient involvement in GDAs.

influence and have an impact on the GDA's activities and practices, and where their roles can be clearly defined.

The areas of GDA governance that were prioritised for patient involvement were communication and outreach activities, data access, and advising data subjects. These are discussed in more detail below.

Communication and outreach activities

According to the participants, communication and outreach activities in which patient involvement can have an impact include engagement activities aimed at reaching the public with a particular message or opening a dialogue with the public on issues pertaining to a GDA's activities. The following were mentioned as possible avenues for patients or their representatives to support GDAs in communication and outreach:

- i. Development of information materials to ensure that the language used is easily understandable and that issues that are important to patients are sufficiently addressed.
- ii. Ensuring accessibility of digital information for persons with disabilities.
- iii. Organising events to help develop programmes that also engage patients and the public.
- iv. Feedback on the clarity and comprehensibility of consent materials.
- v. Development of newsletters to inform patients about the GDA's activities as well as research activities carried out with archived data.
- vi. Developing strategies for communicating research results to patients.
- vii. Establishing networks with patient organisations and researchers in Germany and internationally by organising meetings and joint projects with other patient groups.

Data access

According to the forum participants, having transparent data access procedures with meaningful patient involvement was key to building trust in a GDA. The discussion on data access was focused on GHGA and its data access procedures: It was made clear to the participants in the written information they received prior to the forums as well as in the presentations during the forums that GHGA will not have discretion over who gets access to data. This will be decided by the Data Controllers. Nevertheless, participants saw possibilities for implementing meaningful patient involvement in this area. They noted that transparent data management processes, such as providing information about data and study requests from researchers, are essential for building trust. Participants also felt that there should be opportunities to bring the patient perspective to data access decisions, even if the decisions are ultimately made by other institutions.

Advising data subjects

The forum participants stressed the need for the representatives to be available to advise data subjects when needed. Moreover, patient representatives could play a role in making relevant information available to data subjects. Specific scenarios that were mentioned by the participants included:

- i. Availability to offer advice before a potential data subject consents to secondary research use of their data
- ii. Supporting patients in navigating the research landscape, especially regarding study results relevant to their conditions, and referring them to relevant medical or research personnel
- iii. Advising data subjects on consent withdrawal and removal of data from GDAs.

3.2.2 Resources necessary for patient involvement in GDA Governance

Education of representatives and regular updates

The participants stressed the need for initial training and ongoing education for patient representatives to carry out their responsibilities meaningfully and effectively. According to the participants, relevant topics for patient education include Evidence Based Medicine, the research process, ethical challenges in GDA operations including consent and data sharing, and strategies for effective patient representation. Educational resources should also be made available online in the form of texts, recordings, and tutorial videos. Some of the participants were aware of the work of the *Patienten Experten-Akademie für Tumorerkrankungen*, PEAK (22) in this area, and suggested that collaboration with PEAK could prove helpful.

As pertains specifically to GHGA, the forum participants also stressed the need for regular updates on the goals and progress of GHGA. They acknowledged that the meetings of the various GHGA Working Groups are complex and very time-consuming. As such, regular invitation to or participation in GHGA team meetings would not be practical or productive, and may impede the work and progress of the GHGA Working Groups. However, the participants suggested that representatives could be invited to general meetings where the progress of the GHGA Working Groups is presented.

Acknowledgement and compensation

Involvement in governance will demand significant time from the representatives. Most forum participants reported that they were already occupied with other responsibilities such as family, work, and voluntary activities in their patient groups. They therefore explored what involvement in the govern-

The representatives should be financially compensated for their work on behalf of GHGA.

ance of a GDA would mean for them and how this could best be supported or compensated. The following possibilities were discussed:

- i. Remuneration for the role of patient representative in the GDA
- ii. Allowances for participation in GDA activities including meetings, review of documents, and development of campaigns and initiatives.
- iii. Financial and logistical support for meetings with other patient groups and for other events such as conferences.
- iv. Electronic access to scientific publications and other educational or information resources. This was regarded as being especially important in fulfilling the role of linking the GDA to patient groups, e.g., in helping patients find relevant research results.

3.3 Patient involvement in the governance of GHGA

3.3.1 The form of patient involvement in the governance of GHGA

There was broad consensus that patient involvement in the governance of GHGA would best be achieved through patient representatives. Ideally, patient organisations such as ACHSE and the HKSH (see 2.1) should be involved in the recruitment and education of the representatives. Possible forms of involvement of patient representatives in GHGA governance were discussed during the deliberative forums. These were:

The participants stated that effective patient involvement in GHGA will best be achieved through patient representatives who constitute a Patient Advisory Board (PAB).

- i. integration in currently existing organs and boards (such as outreach and data access procedures) without forming a separate Patient Advisory Board (PAB),
- ii. establishing a PAB,
- iii. both i and ii

During the dialogue event, there was broad support for establishing a PAB whose members are actively involved, where possible, in the meetings, decision-making and activities of the GHGA Working Groups in which their participation would have an impact. Moreover, it was agreed that the PAB should initially have 4 members, 2 each from the cancer and the rare diseases communities, with the possibility of adjusting the size of the PAB in the future, depending on need and newly emerging functionalities of GHGA. It was noted that it would be important to have at least two representatives in each committee or group for them to meaningfully contribute and be heard. The patient representatives should be invited to all meetings of the respective committee or group.

The participants stressed that the PAB members should commit themselves to effectively represent not just issues that are of interest to them, but to all patients. For example, if questions arise concerning a disease with which they do not have any personal experience, they should first consult the relevant patient groups before feeding back that information to the PAB. According to the participants, the PAB should be

represented in GHGA meetings, including the Steering Committee, Members Assembly and the General Assembly. This will foster networking and collaboration between patient representatives and other GHGA members and partners. The forum participants proposed that the PAB should autonomously establish its own operating procedures, which should be congruent to GHGA's mission and objectives. They also suggested that the activities of the PAB should be transparent and results be made publicly available, e.g., on the GHGA website.

3.3.2 Recruitment of patient representatives

The participants stressed the importance of transparency for a legitimate recruitment process. Although various recruitment methods were discussed during the forums, there was consensus during the dialogue event that an application process should be used. An advertisement for the positions of patient representatives should be sent to patients in cancer and rare diseases patient groups. The advertisement should include a clear description of the position and its tasks, as well as its time and competence requirements. The recruitment process should be managed by a recruitment panel, which should, ideally, also have patient representatives.

3.3.3 GHGA events in which patient representatives should be actively involved

The participants stressed the importance of regular interaction and dialogue in meetings between GHGA Working Groups and the patient representatives in GHGA, to develop a common understanding of their different points of view. As far as possible, to make attendance more convenient, the meetings should be online or in a hybrid format. The participants suggested that a biannual meeting format be developed where the GHGA Working Groups present their work and obtain feedback from representatives. They also suggested that the patient representatives be regularly invited to the meetings of the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB).

4. Challenges in the implementation of patient involvement in the governance of GHGA

Identifying the concerns and wishes of patients does not in itself solve the challenge of establishing an appropriate governance model for GHGA. The views, goals, and rights of other stakeholders, including researchers and Data Controllers, should also be considered. Moreover, implementation of patients' expectations should be compatible with the current framework of rules and procedures within which GHGA and its partners operate. Expected challenges or possible areas of tension should be transparently communicated to patients. In this section, we discuss some challenges that may be faced in the implementation of the proposed concept for patient involvement in the governance of GHGA.

4.1 Implementing participants' expectations pertaining to data access within the framework of GHGA's current policies and procedures

Challenges affecting data access decisions are especially relevant within GHGA. From the participants' perspective, patient involvement in data access was a particularly important aspect of appropriate governance. Since GHGA will only have an archive function and no control over data access decisions, the expectation to be involved in data access procedures cannot be met by GHGA in particular. Data access will be granted by Data Controllers through their Data Access Committees (DACs). However, GHGA can develop best practice recommendations for Data Controllers. The function of patient involvement in data access must therefore be clearly defined and carefully implemented.

Roles and opportunities for Data Controllers and researchers

GHGA partners, especially Data Controllers, can play a role in operationalising meaningful patient involvement in data access procedures and increasing its impact. Possible strategies through which patient perspectives could be brought into data access and data use decisions include:

- i. Inviting patient representatives to take part in the normal working procedures of DACs, especially where these do not have trained patient representatives of their own.
- ii. Retrospectively informing patient representatives about data access requests and decisions. Feedback from the patient representatives could then be forwarded to the Data Controllers and considered for future requests.
- iii. Patient representatives being available to support researchers planning to request access to data in GHGA, in the case that the researchers do not have patient representatives with the necessary experience.

These strategies would foster transparency, as they would be opportunities to inform patient representatives about the criteria on which data access decisions are made. They also present an opportunity for Data Controllers: There has recently been a growing political and societal focus on what individuals who give their data for research are entitled to, including knowing what is being done with their data (14). It is increasingly expected that GDAs take proactive roles in engaging with and informing patients and the public, e.g., by making relevant information readily available (23) and enabling direct contact with researchers (24). If supplied with information about data requests, such as proposed projects and the researchers responsible, and with the necessary legal and technical setup, GHGA could support Data Controllers in the task of making this information available for interested patients. This information would also make it possible to monitor data requests, including those granted and rejected, and the reasons for the decisions. Making data access requests available would also make data access procedures more transparent for researchers.

4.2 Education opportunities for patient representatives

Patient education is a necessary component of effective representation (12). A study on activities of patient representatives in Germany showed that they are often not adequately trained to effectively fulfil their roles (25). In addition to giving regular updates on GHGA's activities (see Section 3.2.2 above), comprehensive continuous education and training should be offered to the representatives. Important topics that should be covered were identified by the participants. These should, however, be further explored and expanded, possibly in collaboration with other organisations that are already making progress in this area, such as PEAK.

4.3. Recruitment of patient representatives

The application process described under section 3.3.2 above makes recruitment and patient participation in the governance of GHGA more transparent by making it open to all who receive the advertisement. It is, however, not perfect. Many patients in Germany will not be reached in the call for applications. To help reach patients who are not on the mailing lists of the patient organisations above, the advertisement should also be posted on social media, patient forums, the GHGA website, and the websites of its partner organisations.

5. Conclusion

This white paper proposes a concept for implementing impactful patient involvement in the governance of GHGA based on perspectives of cancer and rare disease patients in Germany. While the concept is specific in its description of the roles of patient representatives, it is also a flexible, adaptable framework, suitable to GHGA's current cultural, social and legal context, and its future objectives. Moreover, it can be adapted for other data infrastructure projects. If implemented, the concept will foster transparency and support the development of a trustworthy GHGA governance structure that meaningfully involves patients. It shall also be a positive step for patient representation in governance of personal health data in Germany.

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